

Work-in-progress Paper Submission for Ubimus 2021:
**Blanket Sounds: An Acoustemological Account of Immersive
Audio and Memory**

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***Abstract.** This project explores the function sound plays in the formation of memory in Ubimus contexts and what influence immersive audio could have in mediating sonic encounters. This is accomplished through the creation of a VR adaptation of a multimedia sculpture called, “The Witness Blanket,” made to memorialize experiences of indigenous survivors of Canadian Residential Schools. This research presents a novel way of communicating auditory information in educational settings through the sonification and musication of sounds that lack real-life sonic equivalents, drawing upon what I call, ‘the semiotics of nostalgia,’ to question the many factors which colour our experience of sound and how our sonic perceptions shape our reality.*

***Keywords.** Sonification, music in education, immersive audio, social interaction in sound and music computing, indigenous cultural preservation, sound and music for VR, timbre in Ubimus contexts.*

1. Introduction

I am the principle sound designer, producer, and engineer for a project creating a virtual reality (or VR) adaptation of a multimedia sculpture called “The Witness Blanket” (or “blanket” for short). Created by artist and indigenous scholar, Carey Newman, the blanket memorializes experiences of indigenous survivors of Canadian Residential Schools. While assembling the blanket, Newman received hundreds of artifacts, stories, songs, letters, and other symbolic pieces from survivors, as well as physical remains from several schools in varying states of neglect, decay, or repurposed use. He collected doorknobs, floor panels, and other remnants from the buildings and surrounding premises. After collecting and organizing these artifacts, he meticulously fit pieces of all different shapes and sizes together to form a complex mosaic panel, visually reminiscent of a quilt, except made out of wood, ceramic, metal, paper, and all manner of other materials aside from what one would expect from an actual blanket.

The piece toured all over Canada for six years, but in light of its physical complexity and the work required to construct, deconstruct, and transport the blanket from one location to another, one can easily begin to see the appeal in a VR version. Aside from the ease of setup (or lack of setup entirely), the other obvious benefit to adapting the blanket for VR is that it allows the piece to become accessible to a global audience.

However, before any attempt can be made to reconstruct the blanket in VR, it is necessary first to deconstruct and examine the nuances and subtleties of the constituent parts that make the analog blanket experience in an effort to identify what makes it sound unique. Those concepts will then be used to design a conceptual framework through which the rest of the audio can be conceived of, produced and organized, and can later help guide the incorporation of audio into the complete VR blanket.

This framing process revealed three central questions about sonic experiencing around which the resulting inquiry has been organized. First, I investigate how sound can be used as a vehicle to facilitate the creation of memory and emotional connection by identifying the variables that influence those connections, as well as researching how, if at all, VR as a medium and 3D audio spatialization techniques can more effectively and/or more powerfully catalyze that process.

Second, I study the ways sound informs our perception of the world by highlighting the effects environmental factors have on acoustic dynamics. I then consider how these dynamics apply to the conceptualization, design, and production of audio for the VR blanket, and finally how the resulting audible products will be used in the subsequent design process. This phase presents opportunities to explore novel representations of music information and challenges notions of agency in performance when the human-machine relationship in a creative and experiential context is blurred and it becomes unclear if the machine is driving the human experience or the human controlling the experience of/in/with the machine. This also raises questions about creative ethics and artistic practices and how to address the implications of our rapidly evolving understanding of human-machine dynamics in the age of AI.

Third, this project contemplates the temporal and ephemeral aspects of sound by studying the fluid relationality of listening, using theories like critical listening positionality and acoustemology to question the many factors that color our experience of sound.

2. Consideration of Auditory Variables

How do we experience sound in the world, and the world through sound? In other words, how do we come to know (and experience) the world through sound, and what can sound tell us about our environment? Sound helps us get oriented in our surroundings and provide us clues about the nature of the place, time, and space we're in. Take for example, the sonic environment of a forest. The sounds of splintering wood could hold a lot of information that had important implications regarding your safety. For example, the quality of the sound would tell you how far you are from the sound

source and the direction it's moving, hopefully giving you enough time to get out of the way of a tree before it falls. But what are we actually hearing when we talk about these functions of sound? What we listen for differs according to the context in which we're listening. For example, direction and movement are helpful considerations when trying to locate sound sources, like with our tree example. If we are able to hear the trunk just as it's beginning to splinter, we will know that the tree is some distance away, but it's not until it starts to fall that we're able to identify that it's falling in our direction.

Changes to Sound Behaviour. So, what variables account for noticeable changes in sound dynamics? The physical environment around a sound directly impacts how the sound behaves and changes depending on the characteristics of the space. Dimensions are one of the primary influences, but the physical materials used in the construction of a space also matter a great deal. Construction style, floor and ceiling materials, and additional nearby matter all affect sound in a space. The physical characteristics of the sound source, its material, size, shape, weight, texture, density, etc. also impact acoustic dynamics. Think of the difference between the sound produced by a falling twig and that made by a falling log. What else or who else is around can also make a big difference, as it certainly does in case of this project. These sounds are subject to the same dynamics and will vary according to a person's size, like their weight or height, the clothes they're wearing (pants versus shorts), the types of shoes they're wearing, their pace or gait, and that's not including spoken sound.

All of these variables become design considerations in the blanket VR adaptation process. How do we deal with the presence of others? Do we design for it and allow the sounds of other to simply become part of the sonic environment, or do we limit the experience to one person at a time? The analog blanket experience obviously involved sounds made by others because others were always present, but here we have the power to exclude that form of sonic interference from a VR adaptation, but think of the significance such a decision would have on the experience. Decisions of that magnitude should not be made without careful consideration and also consulting the artist, as the differences between the two experiences would be profound.

3. Designing Sound Dynamics

Having explained some of the dynamics that influence sound, we can begin thinking about what types of sounds we want to use and how we want them to behave. In attempting to recreate the sonic atmosphere of the original blanket, I first needed to find needed an audible metaphor to link everything together, something to communicate the presence and movement of others. It needed to be personal, intimate, and responsive. My first instinct was to explore the idea of using footsteps. Keen to find ways to embed cultural learning opportunities, I decided to look up footsteps in the Kwakwala language. Kwakwala is spoken by the indigenous people of the north eastern coast of Vancouver Island and blanket artist, Carey Newman. I discovered four separate words

related to the sound of footsteps which suggests a potentially more complex and nuanced understanding of footstep sounds and could be a good opportunity for cross cultural learning. While I haven't yet had an opportunity to consult an expert in this language about the differences in usage, footsteps are easily identifiable, personable, and provide an interesting opportunity for using sound. Footsteps are also a good example because they're universally acknowledged as sounds resulting from our own movement and therefore easily assigned agency to highlight cultural parallels.

Machines Mediating Sonic Experiencing. The consideration of how machines mediate the experience is when things start to get interesting. Firstly, this project begins with the production of audio which is virtually unheard of in VR design. The rationale behind an audio-centric workflow in this case is that it allows for sound to drive other design considerations rather than simply providing auditory fixes to visual cues.

We begin by imagining sounds for things which are naturally silent, and this is where things start to get interesting. By starting the design process with sound, the design of interactions follow naturally. What sound does a braid of hair make? What might you do with it, and what sounds would result from that movement?

The plan is to use eye-tracking data to not only follow the gaze of participants in order to learn about their perceptual instincts within the space, but also allow the system to capture eye-tracking data and use it to guide participants through the space by highlighting objects visually, or even by using sound to call out to people, literally.

4. Creative Implications of the Project

In the introduction to his book, "Hungry Listening: Resonant Theory for Indigenous Sound Studies," Dylan Robinson introduces the concept of colonial listening, and the ways the Canadian residential schools were used to mandate or override culture through listening that he calls the "civilizing sensory paradigm" which he says can be defied through the creation of "culturally immersive learning environments." This is the precise goal of this project: to create a culturally immersive learning environment to foster healing through reflexive listening to indigenous voices telling their own stories.

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